

WATER ICE EXTRACTION FROM ICY LUNAR REGOLITH SIMULANTS USING REDIRECTED SUNLIGHT. A. F.Achorner¹, L. Grill¹, R. Šeško¹, J. Breternitz¹, J.N. Brecher¹ and P.Reiss¹, ¹*Technical University of Munich, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Department of Aerospace and Geodesy, Chair of Lunar and Planetary Exploration (florian.achorner@tum.de)*

Introduction: Water is one of the most abundant resources in the solar system. Its presence was detected on the Moon, asteroids, and other celestial bodies. These water deposits are a promising resource for satellite refuelling, when combined with Water Electrolysis Propulsion (WEP) [1,2]. In the project Ice2Thrust, funded by the European Innovation Council, the Technical University of Munich (TUM) and its partners, aim to develop a self-sufficient space mobility architecture.

One major project goal is the end-to-end demonstration of mining, processing, and utilising water as a source of propellant to generate thrust under relevant conditions. We currently develop an experimental setup for water extraction from icy regolith simulants using redirected simulated sunlight. The sublimated water is captured, liquefied, analysed, and processed for further utilisation in a WEP electrolyser.

It is mounted to a stationary mounting interface thermally connected to the cold table inside the thermal vacuum chamber. In this configuration, the cold trap is mechanically positioned onto the mount using an externally operated rotary and linear feed-through, ensuring effective heat transfer through the physical connection between the mount and the cold trap.

Water captured by the cold trap is subsequently transferred to a custom-designed liquefaction chamber (Figure 1) by removing it from the mount using the manual feedthrough. The liquefaction is then isolated from the thermal vacuum chamber using a gate valve.

Once sealed, the liquefaction chamber is pressurised with nitrogen gas to allow the accumulated ice to liquefy while avoiding contamination of the liquid water with CO₂ from ambient air.

Figure 1: Custom-designed liquefaction chamber with the described valve interfaces.

Experimental setup description: Here, we present the current state of development of the water extraction facility, including the thermal vacuum system, sun simulator, and water retrieval and liquefaction system. The target pressure of the thermal vacuum system is 10⁻⁶ mbar and the target temperature is -120°C, respectively. The sun simulator concentrates the light beam up to 20 solar constants and redirects it to the simulant surface along various paths at adjustable speeds using an optical mirror system.

A movable cold trap collects the water extracted by irradiation with the solar simulator on the icy lunar regolith simulant.

The produced liquid water is collected in a funnel and directed into a storage reservoir. This reservoir can be closed off from the liquefaction chamber to maintain ambient pressure throughout several extraction cycles, as the liquefaction chamber must be evacuated before reopening the gate valve to the main thermal vacuum chamber. Maintaining the storage reservoir in a sealed state prevents re-evaporation of the collected water and ensures that it remains in the liquid phase throughout subsequent operations.

Sample production: It is essential to generate representative simulants of icy lunar regolith for the planned water-extraction experiments. For this purpose, the three mechanical ice-production methods of shaving, blending, and grinding were systematically investigated with the objective of identifying a robust and reproducible technique suitable for laboratory-scale production of water-ice particles.

Each batch of produced ice particles was subsequently separated into four grain-size fractions ($>1000\ \mu\text{m}$, $500\text{--}1000\ \mu\text{m}$, $250\text{--}500\ \mu\text{m}$, and $<250\ \mu\text{m}$) using manual dry sieving. The sieves were pre-cooled to approximately -50°C to minimize thermal input and thereby prevent partial melting of the ice during the sieving process. In addition, the morphology of the resulting particles was examined using an optical microscope with a cold table to preserve the structural integrity of the samples during imaging.

Although the exact morphology of lunar water-ice particles remains uncertain, it is plausible that ice on the lunar surface exhibits highly irregular geometries due to continuous impact-driven regolith gardening [3]. Consequently, the microscopic assessment of particle shape constitutes an important evaluation criterion, ensuring that the laboratory-produced ice particles reflect, as closely as possible, the expected physical characteristics of icy lunar regolith.

Following a structured requirement analysis and concept development process, three experimental setups were designed and implemented. A custom rotational shaver was developed for the shaving approach, while commercially available devices were employed for the blending and grinding methods. All experiments were conducted under low temperature conditions ($\sim -50^\circ\text{C}$) to minimise thermal effects.

The results highlight distinct performance characteristics for each method. The shaving process produced flake-like ice particles but showed mechanical instability, resulting in inconsistent particle sizes and sample contamination. Blending proved effective for rapid particle generation but introduced thermal energy, causing particle sintering and agglomeration, which distorted the size distribution. This thermal effect was successfully mitigated by using dry ice as a coolant during the blending process. Grinding using a burr mill was the most reliable and controllable method, producing sharp-edged, discrete ice particles (Figure 2) without measurable temperature increases. Particle size distribution could be adjusted by varying the burr gap.

Overall, although shaving and blending offer specific advantages due to their high production rates, grinding was identified as the most suitable technique for laboratory-scale generation of water-ice particles intended for icy lunar-regolith simulants. Its superior controllability, high reproducibility, and thermal stability, together with its ability to consistently pro-

duce discrete, sharp-edged particles, position grinding as the most robust and reliable method for simulant preparation under controlled laboratory conditions.

Figure 2: Microscopic image of water ice particles from burr milling, showing sharp-edged, discrete particles.

Summary: The recent developments for the project Ice2Thrust constitute a major step toward establishing a fully integrated laboratory demonstration of in-situ water extraction, collection, and conditioning under relevant conditions. The insights gained from the evaluation of both the water extraction process and the icy sample production methods provide critical information for system optimisation as well as for the scaling potential of the water extraction process toward operational in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) architectures. The ongoing work will therefore support the maturation of technologies required for reliable lunar water ice extraction, contributing to the broader objective of enabling sustainable space mobility and propellant production.

References:

- [1] Mrazek, T. et al (2025), (IAC-25).
- [2] Dengler, S. and Manfletti, C. (2025). (IAC-25)
- [3] Richardson, J. E. and O. Abramov (2020).